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From Water & Sunlight to Thrust: New Propulsion Technologies within the Green SWaP Project

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Abstract

In recent years, interest in developing propulsion technologies based on water as principal propellant has grown exponentially. Water is not only straightforward to manage and stored both on Earth and in space, but it is also abundantly available on numerous celestial bodies within the Solar System, including the Moon. This availability opens game-changing possibilities in the field of In Situ Resource Utilisation (ISRU). Furthermore, water allows for unique synergies with in-space human outposts by means of shared liquid storage and recycling processes. These aspects can significantly enhance the sustainability and feasibility of future space exploration. The Green SWaP project, an EU-EIC Pathfinder initiative, aims to develop the core technologies for future water-based propulsion systems by adopting an innovative approach distinct from previous efforts. The acronym stands for Green Solar-to-Propellant Water Propulsion, reflecting the project's primary objective: the development and validation of technologies that utilize solar energy to co-generate a new combination of propellants from water: hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) and hydrogen (H₂). These propellants serve as starting point to enable the development of two pioneering propulsion technologies. The first is a high-thrust bipropellant engine that utilises concentrated liquid hydrogen peroxide (High Test Peroxide, typical oxidizer for space propulsion applications) and gaseous hydrogen, providing a powerful and efficient main propulsion method. The second is a low-thrust solar thermal propulsion system that employs gaseous hydrogen, offering a sustainable and efficient alternative for long-duration space missions or fine-tuning manoeuvres.

Keywords: Propulsion, Propellant Production, Hydrogen Peroxide, Hydrogen, Bipropellant, Solar Thermal Propulsion

Acronyms/Abbreviations

Green SWaP	Green Solar-to-Propellant Water Propulsion
GEO	Geostationary Earth Orbit
HTP	High-Test Peroxide
ISRU	In-Situ Resource Utilization
MMH	Monomethylhydrazine
NTO	Nitrogen Tetroxide
PEC	Photo/Electrocatalysis
PW	Non-thermal Plasma interaction with Water
SSO	Sun-Synchronous Orbit
STT	Solar Thermal Thruster
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UDMH	Unsymmetrical Dimethylhydrazine
WEP	Water Electrolysis Propulsion

1. Introduction

Space propulsion systems are fundamental to spacecraft operations, enabling functions such as orbital transfers, attitude control, station-keeping, and other critical manoeuvres. In recent years, mission requirements have grown increasingly complex and diverse, driving the development of propulsion systems with far broader capabilities than traditional designs. This evolution is reflected in new technologies that aim to deliver higher performance, improved efficiency and, in some cases, reduced costs [1].

Within the field of space propulsion, bipropellant thrusters have traditionally been preferred for high-performance missions due to their superior efficiency compared to monopropellant options. Historically, bipropellant propulsion has relied on a specific class of hydrazine-based propellants. These propellants, namely pure Hydrazine, Monomethyl Hydrazine (MMH) and Unsymmetrical Dimethyl Hydrazine (UDMH), coupled with Nitrogen Tetroxide (NTO), are commonly valued for their high energy density, long-term storability, and proven exceptional operational track record [2,3]. In addition, the mentioned combinations are hypergolic, igniting spontaneously upon contact, which simplifies ignition systems and contributes to reliable thrust.

These propellants however present major health, safety, and environmental hazards. Handling and transporting such highly toxic and carcinogenic chemicals demand rigorous, costly safety procedures and careful waste management to prevent contamination. In Europe, hydrazine and related compounds are classified as Substances of Very High Concern (SVHC) under the EU's REACH regulation (Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals), raising a concrete chance of future restrictions or bans within the European Economic Area. The regulatory uncertainty around hydrazine, along with the very high costs related to ground operations when such propellants are involved, have accelerated efforts to develop alternative, more environmentally friendly propellants, often referred to as "green propellants". While the term does not have a universally accepted definition, it generally describes propellant options that reduce hazards and simplify handling and storage requirements across all mission phases [4,5].

Among the various options, water is widely regarded as the most promising candidate, not as a chemical propellant itself, but as a source from which several possible chemical propellants can be generated. If it can be established as a viable propellant, it would offer unmatched safety, chemical stability, low cost, and broad availability. Nearly any terrestrial infrastructure can handle water, and extensive material compatibility data already exists. Its suitability for space missions is also highly attractive, opening to concepts such as in-situ resource utilisation (ISRU) and potential integration with life support systems for future human exploration.

These benefits are widely recognised, and there has been relevant effort towards Water Electrolysis Propulsion (WEP). WEP systems split water into hydrogen and oxygen gases via electrolysis, then combust them in a chemical thruster to generate thrust. Despite of the relatively simple architecture of these systems, WEP has also some major limitations [6].

The additional dry mass required by the electrolyser, along with the significant power and thermal demands of the system, are among the main system-level drawbacks. From a performance perspective, both the rate at which propellants can be generated and the reliability of the conversion process present substantial challenges to the entire propulsion system. In addition, the storage of propellants once produced poses equivalent challenges for the chemical compounds' low density, especially hydrogen. Ultimately, these factors lead to higher overall costs compared to conventional propulsion systems. For now, development efforts remain primarily focused on short-duration burns and low-thrust applications.

The project Green SWaP (Green Solar-to-propellant Water Propulsion) aims at producing a different set of propellants from water: concentrated liquid hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) and gaseous hydrogen (H_2), to be then used for different and independent propulsion systems. This approach is very different from classical WEP, and may bring important improvements, as will be discussed in the next section.

2. The Green SWaP Project

Green SWaP is a project funded by the Horizon Europe's European Innovation Council under the Pathfinder Challenge "In-Space Solar Energy Harvesting for Innovative Space Applications". The project, started in October 2024 and lasting four years, is composed by a consortium of leading European universities, research institutions, and industry partners: University of Pisa, Delft University of Technology, University of Turin, Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT), European Research Institute of Catalysis (ERIC) and Novaspace.

The objective of Green SWaP is to prove and validate a technology that will use solar energy to produce propellants (H_2O_2/H_2) in orbit from water for in-space green propulsion. The concept is designed to become a crucial building block to enable innovative green propulsion solutions for in-space services. The approach of producing hydrogen peroxide and hydrogen from water is a novel approach, never developed before. The operation concept evolves by developing two innovative propulsion systems: a main thruster based on the bipropellant combination H_2O_2 and H_2 , and a set of attitude control thrusters based on solar thermal propulsion (STT) utilizing gaseous hydrogen. The solution is studied and applied to specific mission scenarios where the systems developed can be really game-changer options for future in-space mobility.

The production of H_2O_2/H_2 from water using solar energy appears as revolutionary for space applications. The concept has only been preliminary studied for terrestrial applications, and it is not industrially developed yet. The objective of propellants production will be explored during the project using two separate and different approaches: photo/electro catalysis (PEC), and non-thermal plasma interaction with water (PW). Both methods have been tested on Earth to produce H_2O_2 at low concentrations, however in the space environment, abundant light is readily available and there are no external interactions or disturbances to interfere with the process, so the methods are expected to achieve outstanding results. However, dedicated challenges emerge in terms of module compactness, operational conditions, absence of gravity, and the need for automation, which the project will actively work to overcome.

The project aims to explore and advance a wide range of cutting-edge enabling technologies that will surpass the current state of the art and will not focus on a single option. For this reason, the Green SWaP project will compare the two leading alternatives (PEC and PW) and their compatibility with an innovative technology for H_2O_2 concentration based on microfluidic pervaporation.

The PEC approach offers two possible options: a direct photocatalytic approach, where the photocatalyst harvests the light and cogenerates H_2 and H_2O_2 from water, and a combination between a photovoltaic module and an electrocatalytic unit (PV/EC) driven from the photovoltaic module. Both options will be investigated and evaluated for the reference scenario that has been developed in the project.

As a matter of fact, the initial phase of the project includes the definition of a common use-case for the Green SWaP system that includes both the propellant production and the two propulsion system modules.

The overall system set-up and target performance have been studied and agreed upon internally in the consortium during the project's system requirement review (SRR), arriving to the main design parameters shown below:

PARAMETER	REQUIREMENT
Volume Budget	The conversion system internal volume shall not exceed 2.5 m³
Mass Budget	The conversion system mass shall not exceed 200 kg
Power Budget	The conversion system shall not exceed 1.5 kW of electric power
Conversion Panels	The presence of conversion panels shall not exceed a surface of 15 m²
Production Rate	The conversion system shall produce a minimum of 200 g/h of propellants (sum of hydrogen peroxide and hydrogen) at desired concentrations
H_2O_2 Concentration	The conversion system shall deliver hydrogen peroxide with a concentration > 85%
H_2	The purity of Hydrogen shall be > 98% wt.
RCS Thrust Level	The RCS shall provide a vacuum thrust level >1 N

RCS Specific Impulse	The RCS shall achieve a vacuum specific impulse > 500 seconds
Main Thruster Thrust Level	The main thruster shall provide a vacuum thrust level more than 100 N [target 200N]
Main Thruster Specific Impulse	The main thruster shall achieve a vacuum specific impulse > 340 seconds
Main Thruster Reignition Time	The main thruster shall be able to reignite after 30 min
Main Thruster Single Burning Time	The main thruster shall be able to achieve up to 10 min of burning time within the same firing

Table 1: Green SWaP Project Requirements: Integrating Propellant Production with Mission Execution

The main thruster is designed to provide main propulsion for the kick stage module to perform the main orbital maneuvers. Instead, the Reaction Control System (RCS) functions, such as attitude control and orbital maintenance, will be handled by the solar thermal propulsion system presented in the next section.

3. Reference Mission Scenarios

Given the versatile nature of Green SWaP's underlying technologies, a wide range of potential mission profiles are theoretically compatible with the resulting system. During the initial phase of the project, a significant effort was dedicated to ensuring practical relevance and, especially, innovation for future missions.

A structured mission down-selection process was adopted to evaluate a broad range and a relatively large number of viable mission concepts with the system's capabilities. One of the main requirements of the activity was the alignment with project objectives and expected demand within the current and future space market [7,8]. Additional figures of merit, including environmental performance, overall propulsive efficiency, reliability, and cost, as suggested by [1], will be incorporated later in the project to assess the exploitation potential of the technologies developed, both within the context of the project's mission scenario and more broadly in the mission use cases studied as part of the EIC Space Portfolio activities.

The resulting missions covered a diverse range of applications, from orbital debris removal and asset relocation to deep space support and satellite servicing. Each mission was evaluated across multiple criteria with a comparative grading matrix developed to score and rank the options.

The four highest-ranked mission concepts were subject to deeper mission analyses, including detailed assessments of propulsion requirements, operational constraints and target profiles.

This study, which allowed for selecting the most suitable missions to be used as reference scenarios during the project developments, is described in detail in a companion paper presented at the IAC 2025 [9].

From the evaluation process, one mission concept and reference system emerged as the most promising candidate: a reusable orbital kick stage mission. This use case demonstrated the strongest combination of feasibility, practical relevance, and alignment with Green SWaP's technological strengths. It was also identified as the most constrained in terms of performance and system margins, making it an ideal testbed for defining the baseline capabilities and requirements of the Green SWaP infrastructure.

The reference mission utilized during the project is a refuelling station, designed for a wet mass of approximately 2000 kg, operating in a Sun-Synchronous Orbit (SSO) with a dusk-dawn configuration. This orbital choice ensures near-continuous solar exposure, which is essential for sustained power generation and optimal performance of the water-to-propellant conversion process. The refuelling station is only one component of the selected scenario, that includes also a reusable kick stage, capable of diverse missions.

Crucially, the refuelling station will be capable of refuelling at least one kick stage per operational cycle. The station will be designed to rely on a Solar Thermal Thruster (STT) for all orbit maintenance and collision avoidance manoeuvres, eliminating the need for chemical propulsion and reducing operational hazards.

The kick stage is based on a bi-propellant engine for its primary manoeuvres, such as Hohmann transfers and altitude changes, with the STT playing a secondary role in attitude control and precise manoeuvres required for eventual formation flight and docking.

The baseline operational scenario envisions the kick stage retrieving a satellite released into a 200 km circular low Earth orbit and transferring it into a 500 km operational orbit with the same inclination. This baseline defines a minimal but fully representative use case for demonstrating system functionality. More detailed requirements, including specific docking mechanisms, attitude control tolerances, and mission timing, are not defined for the scope of the project.

Figure 1: Green SWaP Reference Mission Scenario

Importantly, the design enables a high degree of flexibility. The system can accommodate off-design missions such as raising satellites to higher altitudes, executing significant inclination changes, or reaching more demanding target orbits. For instance, missions involving smaller satellites or lower target altitudes can allow for total inclination changes of up to 20 degrees. Although scenarios like direct insertion into GEO from highly inclined parking orbits remain outside current capabilities, the inclusion of additional refuelling stations, such as one in lunar orbit or GEO, could significantly expand operational reach in the future.

4. Main Thruster: Bipropellant system based on H_2O_2 and H_2

The Green SWaP main thruster is a bipropellant system that uses liquid high concentration hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) and gaseous hydrogen (H_2) as propellants, both produced from the conversion of water using solar energy. For its nature, a main thruster bipropellant propulsion system necessitates of large quantities of propellants, that may require excessive time for the conversion system to catch up. A critical aspect of the Green SWaP project is then a close coordination between the chemistry and propulsion teams to balance mass, volume, and power budgets, ensuring the feasibility of this use case. Another critical aspect for the thruster is the purity of the propellants, that strongly impacts the performance of the system but that could also create problematic malfunctions if not controlled. From this, the propellant production needs to hold very high purity standard, especially for the concentration of hydrogen peroxide, in order to verify and validate the propulsion system performance.

Given the wide range of missions expected from the kick stage described in the previous section, the thruster is designed to combine high performance with a modular design, allowing flexibility in testing and opening to optimization in later phases. The targeted specific impulse is 340 s, higher than the one of most current liquid-liquid bipropellant combinations that are based on toxic compounds. Unlike many water-based propulsion systems, which rely on the direct electrolysis of water into hydrogen and oxygen and must work in continuous mode directly burning the produced compounds without storage, the Green SWaP project will produce high-grade hydrogen peroxide (HTP) and hydrogen as storable propellants. This enables higher thrust levels and greater mission versatility in terms of achievable maneuvers, since the propellants do not need to be consumed immediately after production.

The design choice of storing the produced propellants introduces technical challenges, including the storage of gaseous hydrogen, the efficient catalytic decomposition of HTP, and the effective mixing of the propellants during injection. Meeting these challenges requires precise control of combustion stability, mixture ratios, and thermal management, all of which are being investigated through the development of a modular prototype architecture.

The prototype development follows the project strategy of implementing two sequential design-implementation-test loops, as displayed in Figure 2. The first loop, starting in October 2025 with the Preliminary Design Review (PDR) of the two propulsion concepts, will focus on component-level validation and is expected to reach TRL 3. The second loop will integrate these components into a complete system, with testing aimed at demonstrating TRL 4.

Figure 2: Green SWaP Phases in increasing TRL

The thruster is being developed to meet the project performance criteria, led by the realization of the mission use cases Table 1. Achieving these objectives requires careful attention to combustion stability, propellant mixture ratios, and thermal management, all of which are investigated through the modular prototype approach, for which the more specific performance criteria are reported below in Table 2.

PARAMETER	SPECIFICATION	ADDITIONAL INFORMATION
<i>O/F Ratio</i>	17.2	Investigated for optimal combustion
<i>Combustion temperature</i>	Dependent on H ₂ O ₂ concentration – around 2600 K	Critical for self-ignition
<i>Thrust Chamber Pressure</i>	10 bar	
<i>Total propellant throughput</i>	400 kg	Total mass of propellant processed by engine, calculated as Burn Time × Mass Flow Rate
<i>Test phases</i>	Two prototypes	First design tested with lab propellants and prototypes; second design with relevant components
<i>Expected TRL</i>	4	Prototype demonstration in lab

Table 2: Green SWaP Main Thruster Performance Parameters

The thruster’s performance, in terms of thrust, specific impulse, and combustion temperature, will be validated using a dedicated testbench. However, initial performance estimates appear promising. Figure 3 and Figure 4 represent the theoretical specific impulse and combustion chamber temperature as function of the oxidizer-to-fuel mass flow rate ratio (ROF) [10].

Generically speaking, the specific impulse measures the efficiency of the propellant consumption in a rocket engine. For a given thrust level, a higher specific impulse allows for lower propellant mass flow rates and therefore more autonomy. The maximum in specific impulse is not achieved at stoichiometric ROF conditions, which is where water propulsion systems must operate since both propellants are generated and directly burnt from water during operations. The stoichiometric ROF values are reported for completeness in Table 3.

Line	Oxidizer	Fuel	Stoich. ROF
—○—	O ₂	H ₂	7.94
—◇—	HTP 98%	H ₂	17.22
—△—	HTP 90%	H ₂	18.75
—□—	HTP 85%	H ₂	19.85
—■—	N ₂ O	MMH	2.50
—◇—	HTP 98%	RP-1	7.39
—*—	N ₂ O	C ₃ H ₆	9.41

Table 3 - Performance Comparison Legend

Figure 3: Specific Impulse Comparison.

Figure 4: Combustion Temperature Comparison.

The performance curves reported in Figure 3 shows that, compared to toxic propellants such as Monomethylhydrazine and Nitrogen Tetroxide (MMH/NTO) and to other green propellant alternatives, HTP/GH2 could reach around 10% higher specific impulse, but not in the stoichiometric condition. Additionally, it is very important that the selected combination HTP/GH2 shows a less narrow operational range in terms of ROF respect to the other combinations. Conventional GO2/GH2 water propulsion yields higher specific impulse, but at the expense of a very steep drop when stoichiometric conditions are not perfectly reached. The other main difference is the extremely high stoichiometric flame temperature, as shown in Figure 4. Contrarily, the relatively high specific impulse provided by the selected combination HTP/GH2 is achieved with relatively low combustion temperature.

NASA CEA predicts up to a 10% reduction in combustion temperature compared to MMH/NTO bipropellants, and up to a 15% reduction compared to conventional GO2/GH2. A lower combustion temperature is desired as it simplifies thermal control and reduces costs by implying less expensive materials. Decreasing the thermal load also greatly improves the combustion efficiency by reducing the amount of propellant dedicated to otherwise necessary active cooling.

Another advantage of Green SWaP's propellants on conventional water propulsion is the high density of HTP. To understand whether this increase of density can offset the loss in mass specific impulse, the volumetric specific impulse can be calculated. It is defined as:

$$I_v = g_0 I_{sp} \rho_{eff} = g_0 I_{sp} \frac{\dot{m}_{fu} + \dot{m}_{ox}}{\frac{\dot{m}_{fu}}{\rho_{fu}} + \frac{\dot{m}_{ox}}{\rho_{ox}}}$$

Figure 5 shows the volumetric specific impulse of the two water-based propulsion options, assuming gaseous storage at 50 bar and ambient temperature.

Figure 5: Volume Specific Impulse Comparison.

Compared to conventional GO₂/GH₂ water propulsion, the HTP/GH₂ combination yields up to 2.5 times higher volume specific impulse. In practical terms, this implies that within the same tank volume, Green SWaP's HTP/GH₂ system can deliver up to 2.5 times more total impulse. This benefit translates into increased usable propellant capacity on board and allows higher thrust levels to be reached without enlarging the propellant storage volume, which can be a very limited resource onboard most spacecraft.

The design prototype deriving from the considerations described above is conceived as a fully modifiable system, enabling rapid interchange and evaluation of critical subsystems.

Figure 6 below, shows a preliminary schematic of the overall prototype and of its different modules.

Figure 6: Overall scheme of Green SWaP modifiable prototype for the main thruster

This schematic highlights clearly the three technologies that the main thruster activity aims to validate:

1. The Catalytic Bed
2. The Injection & Ignition
3. The Combustion and Cooling

The catalytic bed is designed to ensure efficient decomposition of hydrogen peroxide as a compromise between performance and system complexity. One of the main challenges in designing the catalytic bed is maintaining consistent decomposition across variable mass flow rates and hydrogen peroxide concentrations. For the nominal design, the mass flow rate is set for 98%-concentration HTP, while multiple interchangeable nozzles will be manufactured to allow testing at different flow rates without altering the bed geometry. Pressure management is probably the most critical aspect: the bed must operate at higher pressure than the downstream combustion chamber, to prevent backflow, setting nominal bed pressure at values that may become high. The modular assembly of the catalytic bed allows for rapid replacement and testing of different configurations, that will give key data for optimizing the bed in the final thruster design.

The injection and ignition module is tasked with mixing the decomposed hydrogen peroxide, now in the form of hot steam and gaseous oxygen, with gaseous hydrogen to achieve stable ignition and sustained combustion. A key challenge lies in the relatively low mass flow rate of hydrogen compared to hydrogen peroxide, which complicates distribution and effective mixing. Injector design is critical, as it directly affects atomization, vaporization, mixing, and reaction within the combustion chamber. Different injection strategies, including impinging, shear-coaxial, and hybrid designs, are considered based on simplicity, mixing efficiency, and modularity. The module was initially designed with a rapidly replaceable injection plate, incorporating axial holes for decomposed hydrogen peroxide and radial holes for gaseous hydrogen, supported by a cylindrical collection chamber to ensure uniform pressure distribution. Additive manufacturing techniques will be used to enable rapid production of interchangeable plates, allowing flexible adjustment of individual parameters. Cold-flow testing using visualized flow techniques will validate the injection strategy before integration into hot-fire tests.

Finally, the combustion and cooling module is focused on maintaining stable combustion and managing the high temperatures generated during operation. Its main challenges include ensuring combustion stability under varying flow rates and mixture ratios and protecting structural components from thermal stress. The module is designed with modular interfaces to allow testing of alternative cooling strategies and to monitor combustion temperature and pressure, enabling optimization of thermal performance.

Together, these three modules form a fully modular prototype that allows quantification and optimization of the physical parameters critical to the final thruster design. The modular approach not only facilitates rapid replacement and testing of the subsystems but also ensures that the prototype can support iterative development and performance validation under realistic operating conditions.

5. Attitude Control Thruster: Solar Thermal Propulsion

While the solar thermal propulsion concept is promising for auxiliary propulsion, its use within a Reaction Control System (RCS) poses several challenges that must be addressed at both subsystem and mission levels. These challenges arise primarily from the unique operating principles of solar propulsion and the demanding requirements of attitude control, as discussed in In-Orbit Reusable Kick-Stage Enabled by a Sustainable Space Mobility Solution Harvesting Solar Energy for Onboard Fuel Production [11].

First, the attitude control manoeuvres required for the Kick-Stage application imply relatively long thruster activation times. Based on the slew requirements, the average burning time per activation is on the order of 20 seconds, significantly longer than the millisecond-scale pulses typical of chemical or cold-gas RCS thrusters. This constraint impacts control authority for fine manoeuvres and introduces limitations in responsiveness, which must be mitigated through a careful combination of STT operation with reaction wheels or momentum wheels for precision pointing.

Second, the spacecraft must be equipped with a sufficient number of thrusters to guarantee full three-axis controllability. A minimum of 12 STTs is required for redundancy-free operation; however, considering failure tolerance and operational margins, a 16-thruster configuration distributed around the spacecraft is assumed, in line with conventional RCS architectures. This increases system complexity in terms of mass, volume, thermal shielding, and propellant feed lines, particularly given the hydrogen compatibility and leakage prevention requirements discussed earlier.

Third, the operational lifetime of the solar propulsion-based RCS introduces stringent demands on component durability. The system is expected to withstand at least 3,500 ignition cycles throughout its operational life. Unlike conventional bipropellant or monopropellant thrusters, where ignition cycles are relatively short and energetically modest, solar propulsion cycles involve heating the absorber and nozzle materials to high temperatures with each firing. This repeated thermal cycling introduces risks of material fatigue, hydrogen embrittlement, and degradation of seals or joints.

Finally, the thrust modulation and impulse-bit generation represent a non-trivial challenge. The nominal thrust of 1 N is orders of magnitude higher than the torques required for counteracting environmental disturbances, which are on the order of 10^{-5} Nm. Consequently, solar thruster would operate far below their nominal performance envelope in case of a failure of the reaction wheels, relying on throttling or pulsed firing modes. This necessitates precise thermal and flow control strategies to avoid overshooting attitude corrections, while still enabling efficient operation during larger manoeuvres such as slews, momentum dumping, or pre-manoeuve reorientations.

In order to meet the requirements for attitude control and the precise manoeuvres foreseen for the reference mission scenarios, Green SWaP project will develop a Solar Thermal Thruster (STT) propulsion system suitable to perform these tasks. The development will bring the technology from the current TRL2 to TRL4 with the design and testing of a prototype that can generate 1 N of nominal vacuum thrust and has a vacuum specific impulse of no less than 500 s, using hydrogen as propellant.

The STT propulsion system can mainly be divided into 3 components: the solar collector, the light absorber/heat exchanger and the nozzle. A schematic representation of the system can be seen in Figure 7 [12].

Figure 7: STT scheme

The solar collector is typically a concave reflecting surface (or an array of surfaces) that allows to concentrate the incident sunlight into the absorber cavity. The absorber/heat exchanger is a component that receives the solar radiation, transforms this radiation into heat and exchanges the heat with the propellant. The nozzle, as in other more conventional propulsion concepts, accelerates the heated propellant, changing its thermal energy into kinetic energy in order to generate thrust. Additionally, hydrogen is theoretically the best possible propellant for this type of system in terms of specific impulse, given its low molar mass it's possible to achieve up to 1100 seconds of specific impulse [12,13].

The STT concept was initially proposed more than 60 years ago, but it has not been fully demonstrated in space until now. Using the solar light to heat up the propellant to potentially very high temperature gives higher specific impulse with medium thrust levels, covering the gap between chemical and electrical propulsion. The aim of Green SWaP is to advance the technology readiness of this space propulsion technology by demonstrating one or more STT concepts in view of their future use in actual space systems.

The specific impulse that can be obtained with a STT is directly linked to the temperature of the propellant upstream the nozzle (chamber temperature) and the propellant itself. The reachable I_{sp} values are reported in the Figure 8.

Figure 8: STT specific impulse

The first prototype for the STT was developed as an innovative upper stage main engine. The test of the first prototype developed by Shoji [13] had a thrust of 3.69 N and a specific impulse slightly above 800 s; the temperature of the hydrogen propellant at the end of the heat exchanger reached about 2777 K. Despite the promising performance of the engine, the STT as the main engine was not considered for an upper stage for two main reasons: the challenges associated to hydrogen storage and the big concentrators (and related structures and pointing requirements) needed.

For the Green SWaP application, the hydrogen storage issues are alleviated thanks to the in-orbit production of propellant and the development of an innovative concept of inflatable tank, which is also part of the project. A cryogenic storage tank is not required anymore since hydrogen is produced in orbit in gaseous state, from water.

More recent technology advancements, such as the maturation of the optic fibre concept, have allowed to alleviate other issues associated to the development of STT thrusters: by using multiple smaller solar concentrators, it is now possible for the light to be radiated into the absorber cavity independently of the satellite pointing. The first to introduce this idea were Kennedy and Palmer [14] at the Surrey University. They developed a STT prototype that could also be used for small satellites, but using the significantly less performant (and more toxic) hydrazine instead of hydrogen.

The solution proposed for transporting the concentrated solar light from small concentrators using optic fibres is still retained as the best option for STT design; therefore, Green SWaP project will not design a concentrator system but will assume that the light is collected and concentrated with a similar system as the one proposed by Kennedy and Palmer.

Given the in-space use of the thruster, the nozzle design will be optimized to generate the nominal 1 N thrust in vacuum. The trade-off between the most common geometries will take into consideration the heat loss due to radiation and the mounting of the thruster into the spacecraft. Given the purposes of attitude control and precise manoeuvring, the nozzle shall be as light as possible, and the exit plume shall not interfere with any of the spacecraft surfaces.

The key feature in order to achieve the required specific impulse is the maximum temperature to which the propellant is heated. To optimize this parameter, multiple design options for the heat exchanger will be designed and tested. The minimum temperature in order to meet the specific impulse requirement is around 1300 K; to make this possible, the high-temperature parts of the thruster shall be manufactured with materials that can withstand these temperature levels, such as Rhenium, Molybdenum, ceramic materials or Tungsten. On top of it, the material must be compatible with the hydrogen flow and shall have good structural resistance at high temperatures. Including due consideration of the possible embrittlement caused by the contact with hydrogen.

During the identified reference missions, sunlight will not always be available and the attitude of the spacecraft during mating operations or manoeuvres is not always ideal to concentrate the solar light into the absorber. For these reasons there is necessity to design a system able to maintain the requested propulsion performance even if there is no sunlight available. One possible solution might be the use of phase-change materials to store the heat power from the solar radiation and release it gradually when required. Another option might be to use higher melting temperature materials, designing the thruster to minimize heat losses in order to still have the material above the minimum required temperature during the shadow orbit periods. Both solutions will be studied and eventually included in the design options developed and tested by Green SWaP.

The STT is intended for use in auxiliary propulsion, which requires the thruster to be compact, highly reliable, and capable of delivering low impulse bits on demand. Among the various absorber cavity designs investigated by Shoji [13], the most suitable is the windowless cavity.

In a windowless cavity, solar energy is absorbed directly at the surface of a pressure vessel and transferred to the propellant via convection through the vessel wall. In contrast, a windowed cavity uses a transparent window to transmit solar energy into the cavity, where it comes into direct contact with the propellant. Another approach involves particulate absorption, in which an opaque seeding material is injected into the working fluid to absorb solar energy; the seedant is subsequently exhausted along with the propellant.

Windowless cavities are considered more appropriate for this application due to several advantages: it eliminates the need for a window cooling system, avoids the inclusion of rotating components, and does not require suspended materials that could degrade propulsion performance. The cavity's size and geometry will be optimized to minimize losses of incident solar radiation.

The use of hot hydrogen as propellant is the best choice for propulsion purposes but is introducing additional, significant challenges. Next to the need for a system that can handle high temperatures, all materials in direct contact with the propellant must be compatible with hydrogen and the system and the propulsion system shall meet the standard leakage requirements, which are significantly more challenging when associated to the low molar mass and low density of gaseous hydrogen. Common high temperature sealings are manufactured from carbon base materials, typically not compatible with hydrogen. New sealing designs or methods will be studied and tested in order to keep hydrogen leakage within acceptable limits.

Key of the development process is the testing approach: each subcomponent will be tested initially in a standalone configuration and when possible, in scaled conditions (for example, with different propellants), in order to verify the design and its functioning in accordance with the mathematical models developed by the team. The final prototype, including the most promising heat exchanger and nozzle geometries, will be tested in fully assembled configuration and in a relevant environment, in order to assess the full performance of the thruster. To facilitate this testing strategy, a completely new test bench, specifically targeted to STT testing, will be developed within Green SWaP by the TU Delft team.

If the prototype reaches the desired performance, it will be to the best of the authors' knowledge the first demonstrator of solar thermal thruster with this performance, suitable for auxiliary propulsion, using hydrogen as propellant.

6. Conclusions

The Green SWaP project establishes a novel framework for water-based in-space propulsion by producing liquid hydrogen peroxide and gaseous hydrogen through an innovative process that departs from classical electrolysis.

Following an extensive state-of-the-art review, the project team already selected a reusable orbital kick stage mission, anchored by a 2,000 kg refueling station in a Sun-Synchronous dusk-dawn orbit, as our reference scenario. This configuration offers the tightest performance margins and the greatest practical relevance, making it an ideal proving ground for Green SWaP's core technologies.

At the heart of the system lie two pioneering thrusters. The primary engine employs an $\text{H}_2\text{O}_2/\text{H}_2$ bi-propellant combination to execute major maneuvers such as Hohmann transfers and orbital changes, while an array of solar thermal thrusters using gaseous hydrogen will provide orbit maintenance, collision avoidance, attitude control, and precision docking capabilities. By eliminating conventional chemical propellants, this dual-thruster architecture promises enhanced safety, simplified logistics, and reduced environmental impact, opening to new future missions.

Although both mentioned propulsion systems currently have a relatively low technology maturity in terms of technology readiness levels, Green SWaP's roadmap emphasizes rapid prototyping, iterative testing, and systematic maturation throughout the project lifecycle.

By advancing these concepts toward higher maturity, the project aims to unlock sustainable, reusable spacecraft architectures and enable the way for future missions that improve the leverage of water's unrivalled potential as an in-space propellant.

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